

Science of the Total Environment

Streets classification models by urban features for road traffic noise estimation

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	STOTEN-D-24-06616R1
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	Road traffic noise; Urban sound environment; Sustainable Urban Planning; multinomial ordered logistic regression
Corresponding Author:	Guillermo Rey Gozalo, Ph.D. Universidad de Extremadura Escuela Politecnica Cáceres, SPAIN
First Author:	Alexandra L. Montenegro
Order of Authors:	Alexandra L. Montenegro Guillermo Rey Gozalo, Ph.D. Jorge P. Arenas Enrique Suárez
Abstract:	<p>Road traffic is the primary source of environmental noise pollution in cities. This problem is also spreading due to inadequate urban expansion planning. Hence, integrating road traffic noise analysis into urban planning is necessary for reducing city noise in an effective, adaptable, and sustainable way. This study aims to develop a methodology that applies to any city for the stratification of urban roads by their functionality through only their urban features. It is intended to be a tool to cluster similar streets and, consequently, traffic noise to enable urban and transportation planners to support the reduction of people's noise exposure. Three multivariate ordered logistic regression statistical models (Model 1, 2, and 3) are presented that significantly stratify urban roads into five, four, and three categories, respectively. The developed models exhibit a McFadden pseudo-R² between 0.5 and 0.6 (equivalent to R² greater than 0.8). The choice between Model 1 or 2 depends on the scale of the city. Model 1 is recommended for developed cities with an extensive road network, while Model 2 is most suitable in intermediate and growing cities. On the other hand, Model 3 could be applied at any city scale but focused on local management of transit routes and for designing acoustic sensor installations, urban soundwalks, and identification of quiet areas. Urban features related to road width and length, presence of transport infrastructure, and public transport routes are associated with increased traffic noise in all three models. These models prove useful for future action plans aimed at reducing noise through strategic urban planning.</p>

Highlights

- Stratification of urban roads by their urban features.
- Urban features-based multinomial ordered logistic regression models.
- Street categorization method for validation measurements of road traffic noise maps

1 **Streets classification models by urban features for road traffic noise estimation**

2 Alexandra L. Montenegro^a, Guillermo Rey-Gozalo^{b*}, Jorge P. Arenas^a, Enrique Suárez^a.

3 ^aLABACAM, Instituto de Acústica, Universidad Austral de Chile, Valdivia, Chile.

4 ^bLaboratorio de Acústica (Lambda), Departamento de Física Aplicada, Instituto Universitario de
5 Investigación para el Desarrollo Territorial Sostenible (INTERRA), Escuela Politécnica, Universidad
6 de Extremadura, Avda. de La Universidad, s/n, 10003 Cáceres, Spain.

7 * Corresponding author: guille@unex.es

8 **Abstract**

9 Road traffic is the primary source of environmental noise pollution in cities. This problem is also
10 spreading due to inadequate urban expansion planning. Hence, integrating road traffic noise analysis into
11 urban planning is necessary for reducing city noise in an effective, adaptable, and sustainable way. This
12 study aims to develop a methodology that applies to any city for the stratification of urban roads by their
13 functionality through only their urban features. It is intended to be a tool to cluster similar streets and,
14 consequently, traffic noise to enable urban and transportation planners to support the reduction of
15 people's noise exposure. Three multivariate ordered logistic regression statistical models (Model 1, 2,
16 and 3) are presented that significantly stratify urban roads into five, four, and three categories,
17 respectively. The developed models exhibit a McFadden pseudo- R^2 between 0.5 and 0.6 (equivalent to
18 R^2 greater than 0.8). The choice between Model 1 or 2 depends on the scale of the city. Model 1 is
19 recommended for developed cities with an extensive road network, while Model 2 is most suitable in
20 intermediate and growing cities. On the other hand, Model 3 could be applied at any city scale but focused
21 on local management of transit routes and for designing acoustic sensor installations, urban soundwalks,
22 and identification of quiet areas. Urban features related to road width and length, presence of transport
23 infrastructure, and public transport routes are associated with increased traffic noise in all three models.

24 These models prove useful for future action plans aimed at reducing noise through strategic urban
25 planning.

26 **Keywords:** Road traffic noise; urban sound environment; sustainable urban planning; multinomial
27 ordered logistic regression.

28 **1. Introduction**

29 Living in a sustainable city provides high-quality housing, livelihoods, and services for its residents,
30 ensuring their availability for the future. One of the United Nations' goals (Goal 11) is to make cities and
31 communities sustainable. One of the key targets to achieve this goal is to enhance inclusive and
32 sustainable urbanization and the planning capabilities of agglomerations by 2030 (UN, 2015). However,
33 many cities worldwide are unsustainable, affected by air, soil, water, and noise pollution and limited
34 mobility options (Kyprianou et al., 2023). It has been observed that the primary source of noise in cities
35 is road traffic, and the limited understanding of the urban sound environment in urban and transportation
36 planning is causing the progressive spread of this environmental pollutant year after year (UN-Habitat,
37 2022).

38 Road traffic noise is being periodically studied in major cities through noise mapping since it is a global
39 health problem recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2018), and it is a mandatory
40 practice in European Union member countries (EC, 2002). The analysis of these maps has reported that
41 almost 60 million city residents are exposed to road traffic noise levels above 55 dBA during the day,
42 evening, and night (Khomeiko et al., 2022). Prolonged exposure at these noise levels can cause hearing
43 damage, annoyance, mortality, sleep disturbance (awakening), and interfere with cognitive processes,
44 strongly affecting the quality of life (WHO, 2018).

45 Reducing 30% of people chronically exposed to transportation noise is the goal of the Zero Pollution
46 Action Plan by 2030 (EC, 2022). Thus, current noise reduction measures must be intensified to achieve

47 this reduction. Optimized noise barriers, noise control at building facades, and low-noise tire paving
48 material are the most implemented noise mitigation methods (Ranpise & Tandel, 2022). Noise control
49 on facades or using low-noise tires and quiet road surfaces can provide reductions of up to 10 dB (EC,
50 2017; Rey-Gozalo et al., 2022). Barriers can reduce the noise up to 15-20 dB (EC, 2017; Rey-Gozalo et
51 al., 2022). Nevertheless, considering noise pollution in urban and transportation planning is one of the
52 challenges for the cities of tomorrow (UN-Habitat, 2022) because it is potentially the most effective,
53 adaptable, and sustainable action to reduce people's noise exposure. Still, there needs to be more data
54 available to quantify it on a city scale (Blanes et al., 2022).

55 Studies conducted in cities worldwide have shown the significant contribution of urban form on noise
56 levels (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2018). Noise mapping (Montalvão et al., 2011; Wang & Kang, 2011;
57 Weber et al., 2014; Margaritis & Kang, 2016; Yu & Kang, 2017; Kim et al., 2019) and *in situ* noise
58 measurements (Han et al., 2018; Hong & Jeon, 2017; Lu et al., 2019) have been used to analyze urban
59 features and morphology effects in road traffic noise of cities.

60 Noise mapping results were used by Montalvão et al. (Montalvão et al., 2011) to analyze the influence
61 of urban shapes on road traffic noise in Aracaju city (Brazil), concluding that the number of building
62 floors, street profiles related to building façades and its spatial distribution were underline aspect to
63 design streets to minimize the effects of urban traffic noise in built environments. Also, Wang and Kang
64 (Wang & Kang, 2011) studied cities in UK and China to compare the effects of urban morphology
65 (accessible space coverage, building coverage, and road coverage) on the traffic noise distribution
66 patterns projected at ground and at building façades. Their results demonstrated that cities with different
67 population densities significantly differ in noise distribution, and their urban morphology considerably
68 affected traffic noise. Weber et al. (Weber et al., 2014) applied landscape metrics to predict noise and
69 particulate matter patterns in Leipzig (Germany). They found that the Shannon's diversity index and
70 evenness index related to land use, as well as patch density and edge density associated with the geometry

71 of the built environment, are landscape metrics correlated to the highest levels of noise and air pollution
72 modeled in apartment blocks and village areas with suitable spaces for daily shopping, communication,
73 transport, and leisure. They concluded that landscape metrics are more useful and fit statistically better
74 than structural parameters such as construction height, total area, or percentage of built area. Margaritis
75 and Kang ([Margaritis & Kang, 2016](#)) analyzed eight UK cities with two different forms (radial and linear)
76 considering urban levels of macro-scale, mesoscale, and micro-scale to investigate the relationship
77 between a total of 18 urban features of morphology related to green spaces (ratio and pattern), roads or
78 buildings, census geodemographic data and traffic noise distribution calculated from public noise maps
79 reconstruction. They found significant relationships between some of these urban variables and day-
80 evening-night noise levels at different scales. Green space patterns, street characteristics (connectivity
81 and hierarchy), land use and geodemographic attributes (population and car availability) were the
82 common explanatory variables in all scales. Yu and Kang ([Yu & Kang, 2017](#)) studied the relationship
83 between different urban morphological parameters and the potential effect of road traffic noise on
84 outdoor sound propagation in villages in China. For different distances between motorway and villages,
85 they found that while the shape complexity of the whole landscape increases, the noise zone in the village
86 decreases. They concluded that it is possible to expand the quiet zones in villages by controlling the
87 landscape shape index of buildings and villages roads defined by their circumference boundary and total
88 area of the buildings and roads, respectively. Kim et al. ([Kim et al., 2019](#)) guided by the results published
89 by Hunjae et al. ([Hunjae et al., 2017](#)) utilized the available road traffic noise maps of Gwangju
90 Metropolitan City (South Korea) to calculate noise values for each grid in the study area and to extract
91 population, buildings, roads (with traffic volume and speed included), and land use. Subsequently, they
92 build and compared an artificial neural network model and an ordinary least-squares model, resulting in
93 both models predicting road traffic noise with similar R^2 of 0.50 and 0.44, respectively. The most
94 important urban form indicators related to road traffic noise levels of both models were floor space index

95 (building height) and ground space index (building density), followed by land uses areas such as
96 industrial, residential, and commercial.

97 On the other hand, Han et al. (Han et al., 2018) used *in situ* measurements of road traffic noise to
98 investigate how the urban morphology of the Shenzhen metropolitan region of China was correlated to
99 regional environmental noise and traffic noise (with vehicle flow data) through socioeconomic
100 morphology data and geographical landscape metrics of the urban area. They concluded that traffic land
101 is the greatest contributor to urban regional environmental noise, followed by mixed residential and
102 commercial land use. Furthermore, Hong and Jeon (Hong & Jeon, 2017) performed a multiple linear
103 regression analysis to explore the relationship between urban morphological indicators and measured
104 acoustics parameters among spatiotemporal pattern soundscape in Seoul (Korea). Using L_{Aeq} , they
105 concluded that open space (square and city stream areas) and water feature components explained
106 approximately 50% of the variance of pleasantness.

107 Lu et al. (Lu et al., 2019) developed structural equation models to explore the effect of three different
108 road features on traffic noise through traffic flow using data from field measurements in Dalian City,
109 China. The results showed that lane number (road width measure based on the number of lanes)
110 influences the traffic noise mainly as a function of the traffic flow rate, so more lanes indicate increased
111 traffic demand due to connected urban land and increasing noise amplitude. In addition, road segment
112 length (distance between two adjacent motor vehicle intersections) affects traffic noise directly
113 proportional to higher vehicle speeds, leading to increased noise intensity. Finally, road junctions
114 (classified according to the presence or absence of traffic lights) have significant direct effects on noise
115 intensity and amplitude, considering that drivers accelerate or decelerate in the middle of the road
116 between intersections.

117 Statistical modeling techniques and geographical information on urban features have been used in
118 combination with traffic volume to estimate urban road traffic noise maps. Predictor variables such as
119 wind speed, digital elevation model, road networks, area of residential density, land use area (residential,
120 industrial, and green areas), and other urban variables (gas stations, bus stops, bus lanes, traffic lights,
121 intersections, and toll road) have been used. In a study conducted in Shah Alam (Malaysia), Adulaimi et
122 al. ([Adulaimi et al., 2021](#)) employed a land use regression (LUR) model based on machine learning,
123 statistical regression, and geographical information systems. Their findings showed that primary road
124 type and bus stops were the most important variables in predicting noise maps. In addition to traffic
125 volume and others, public transport and land use had a significant impact on noise level prediction. In
126 Cheongju (South Korea), Hunjae et al. ([Hunjae et al., 2017](#)) regressed road traffic noise with the average
127 urban form to develop an ordinary least-squares model, spatial autoregressive model, and spatial error
128 model. Factors such as ground space index, floor space index, traffic volume, traffic speed, road area
129 density, and the fraction of industrial area were significant on the noise level estimation. Harouvi et al.
130 ([Harouvi et al., 2018](#)) also developed a LUR model in Israel using variables associated with noise sources
131 (i.e., vehicle volume).

132 In addition, transportation urban studies such as the travel behavior approach reveal which routes and
133 transportation modes are preferred in the city, determining in the long term the functionality of an urban
134 road. In this context, travel forecasting research considers that several demographic burden urban features
135 related to the inhabitants of the surrounding area are the principal explanatory variables for trip
136 generation models ([Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2011](#)). Age, gender, income, work status, education level,
137 family size, cost, and availability of travel modes (public buses, cycling, taxi services, etc.) are the most
138 important factors influencing travel demand in developing cities ([Mwale et al., 2022](#)). With a different
139 approach, sidewalks and bicycle lanes located on streets canyon have been evaluated through modeling

140 several geometric designs. Some shapes were found to reduce the road traffic noise affecting pedestrians
141 and urban cyclists using active modes of transportation in cities ([Echevarria Sanchez et al, 2016](#)).

142 Case studies indicate progress, but more city-level evidence is needed. Therefore, it is essential to cluster
143 similar city roads to extend the geographical analysis by knowing which and where the urban features
144 influence its functionality and, consequently, traffic noise. The location through the streets of some urban
145 features is already considered in other dimensions of sustainable planning, such as walkability ([Li et al.,
146 2023](#)) and mobility, since they are considered trip generators ([ITE, 2010](#)). Still, their relationship with
147 environmental noise has yet to be sufficiently studied on a city scale. This knowledge will allow urban
148 and transportation planners to determine the future functionality of the road according to its urban design
149 and planned facilities. It also allows acoustic engineers to design data collection campaigns for the
150 validation of road traffic noise maps, mainly because traffic information is generally not available for an
151 entire city since traffic is often measured, simulated, and forecasted to reduce congestion in the main
152 roads even in new technologies and infrastructure developments ([Shaygan et al., 2022](#)).

153 This study aims to develop a methodology applicable at the city level for the stratification of urban roads
154 by their functionality through only their urban features. It is intended to be a tool to cluster similar streets
155 to allow planners to support the reduction of people's noise exposure by offering probabilistic models
156 applicable to developed and growth cities based on typical urban data on city streets. The functionality
157 of urban roads is related to their use, which, as previous studies in cities located in different countries
158 and with a wide range of population size have shown, allows to stratify and determining noise levels with
159 a suitable accuracy ([Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a](#); [Barrigón Morillas et al., 2018](#); [Rey Gozalo et al., 2020](#)).

160 The first section of the article describes the research study area and their urban relevance. Valdivia, one
161 of the main cities in southern Chile which has a growing population within a natural setting, where much
162 of it lives in the urban zone ([INE, 2017](#)). Although its urban form constantly changes due to adaptation

163 to natural disasters and unplanned urban growth, Valdivia has been rated for many years as one of the
164 best and most desirable cities to live in the country (Zumelzu et al., 2016). Therefore, it is crucial to
165 maintain or improve the city's quality by taking care of its acoustic environment. Subsequently, the
166 procedure for registering urban and sound data is detailed, along with the processing for analysis. Finally,
167 the main results are presented and discussed. Three urban features-based models have been developed
168 with high performance for stratifying urban roads in relation to their road traffic noise.

169 **2. Methods**

170 *2.1. Study area*

171 The area covered by this study corresponded to the city of Valdivia, with a population of 166,080
172 inhabitants, 93.2% of them living in the urban area. Hence, its population is in the range of 100,000 to
173 300,000 inhabitants, classifying it as an intermediate-sized city according to various international
174 organizations (OECD et al., 2021; UN-Habitat, 2022). The importance of studying an intermediate city
175 comes from the fact that these urban areas host at least 50% of the world's population (UN-Habitat, 2006)
176 and are experiencing faster population growth as they have the capacity and attractiveness to grow (UN-
177 Habitat, 2022). In Chile, 47% of the population resides in cities with fewer than 300,000 inhabitants
178 (INE, 2017). The city's main economic activity is commerce (INE, 2017), where an important
179 commercial activity is distributed around the historic city center and major roads. Valdivia is a dynamic
180 city that has experienced many changes in its urban form due to economic factors and natural catastrophic
181 events. Consequently, the urban environment and its roads are mainly curved, surrounded by natural
182 open spaces. Numerous neighborhoods have been built along the natural limits of rivers, wetlands, and
183 forests.

184 The main access and exit road to the city is Ramón Picarte Avenue (see Fig. S1), which has many shops
185 and facilities. The area has experienced significant population growth in recent years. This is the most

186 integrated street in the city at a global level, according to its most recent aerial axial map (Zumelzu et al.,
187 2016). Therefore, this avenue represents the morphological center where people probably prefer to travel
188 since it is the least segregated street (Zumelzu & Barrientos-Trinares, 2019). Arturo Prat Ave. is also a
189 major urban road that runs through the city alongside the main river. It connects other urban roads from
190 the bridge that provides access to the city from the north to essential services such as healthcare facilities,
191 stores, schools, and other city areas. Therefore, it is an alternative urban road to Ramón Picarte Ave. for
192 accessing the city center, and it has a high aesthetic value due to its proximity to the Calle Calle River.

193 Valdivia has two other closest major urban zones: Teja Island (Isla Teja) and Las Animas, both connected
194 by bridges (see Fig. S1). Teja island is characterized by the beauty of its urban parks, museums,
195 restaurants, pubs, and the main campus of the University Austral of Chile, which hosts around 14,000
196 students. Roads to residential and mixed areas connect all these places of interest. Meanwhile, Las
197 Animas has industrial facilities and naval services. This area is reached by people entering Valdivia from
198 the north via Pedro Aguirre Cerda Ave. This avenue connects access roads to the industrial site and
199 residential neighborhoods of the zone. Consequently, the functional importance of Los Robles Street and
200 Pedro Aguirre Cerda Ave., which connect these two urban areas, is evident.

201 2.2. *Measurement procedure*

202 The urban roads of Valdivia were the experimental unit. One hundred forty urban roads were randomly
203 selected by their typology and abundance in the city (see Table S1 and Fig. 1). For this purpose, the urban
204 roads were previously classified into five different categories according to their functionality by using a
205 previously developed methodology known as the categorization method (Rey Gozalo et al., 2020;
206 Barrigón Morillas et al., 2018).

- 207 • Category 1 (C1): Preferential streets for connection with other cities and interconnection of those
208 preferential streets.

- 209 • Category 2 (C2): Streets that provide access to the primary distribution nodes of the city. It also
- 210 includes roads used as alternatives to C1 streets in traffic congestion.
- 211 • Category 3 (C3): Streets that lead to regional roads, streets that provide access from C1 and C2 streets
- 212 to centers of interest in a city (hospitals, shopping malls, etc.), and streets that clearly allow communication
- 213 between C1 and C2 streets.
- 214 • Category 4 (C4): Includes all other streets that allow communication between C1, C2, and C3
- 215 streets, as well as the main streets of principal neighbourhoods that were not included previously
- 216 • Category 5 (C5): Includes all the rest of the streets of the city except pedestrian-only streets

217
218 **Fig. 1.** Urban road types of categorizations, road traffic noise sampling points, and census demographic data.

219 To analyze the functionality of the 140 total urban roads sampled, 91 different urban features were

220 collected. In the first step, each street was biked and observed. Simultaneously to the noise

221 measurements, multimodal urban transportation and built environment elements were identified for each

222 road. Likewise, temporary residential buildings, equipment buildings, and recreational areas of each road

223 were visited in the same week of the noise measurement. Afterward, distances and areas were measured
 224 *in situ* and by using the Google Earth Pro ruler tool. Finally, demographic burden features were extracted
 225 from the 2017 Census data shapefile (INE, 2017).

226 Overall, building use types, recreational areas, multimodal transportation, built environment elements,
 227 and demographic burden data were chosen to group the urban features studied. All urban features
 228 collected are available in Fig. 2 and Fig. S2.

229

230

Fig. 2. Urban features diagram

231 Firstly, nursing homes (V₁), hostels or cottages (V₂), and hotels (V₃) were considered temporary
 232 residential buildings (V₅). On the other hand, concerning equipment buildings (V₄₆) a total of forty urban
 233 features were clustered among commercial buildings (V₆–V₁₆), religious facilities (V₁₇–V₁₉), cultural
 234 buildings (V₂₀–V₂₄), sport facilities (V₂₅–V₂₈), educational buildings (V₂₉–V₃₄), health facilities (V₃₅–
 235 V₃₈), security facilities (V₃₉–V₄₁), service buildings (V₄₂–V₄₄), and community centers (V₄₅). All the
 236 building use types of urban features were recorded for each road. The procedure is first to count all the

237 units having access through the road and then weight them according to the road length in kilometers
238 (km). Consequently, the unit of measurement is called #/km (see Fig. S2).

239 Moreover, the surface of recreational areas (V₄₉) were identified and traveled through for each road.
240 Public and private parks were allocated as green areas (V₄₇), and public squares were considered as part
241 of public space (V₄₈). The calculated surface of the recreational area included only the space intended
242 for people and pet's use. These variables (V₄₇–V₄₉) were determined by satellite images and expressed
243 in hectares (ha).

244 Multimodal urban transportation elements comprise urban features related to road design made for
245 vehicles and pedestrian interaction within the city. Specifically, they are transportation infrastructure
246 (V₅₀–V₅₃), geometrical design or lanes (V₅₄–V₅₈), multimodal transportation lane types (V₅₉–V₆₃),
247 intersections (V₆₄–V₆₆), maximum vehicle speed (V₆₇), security elements (V₆₈–V₇₀), place of interest and
248 other cities sign (V₇₁–V₇₂). Additionally, transit and taxi stops (V₇₃–V₇₄), effective transit routes (V₇₅)
249 designed for the city, and different public parking (V₇₆–V₈₂) were included.

250 Regarding transportation infrastructure (V₅₀–V₅₃), security elements (V₆₈–V₇₀), location signs (V₇₁–V₇₂)
251 and public transportation stops (V₇₃–V₇₄), all the units accessible along the road were counted and
252 weighted by the length of the road in kilometers. Similar to the previous variables (V₁–V₄₆), the unit of
253 measurement is defined #/km. Geometrical lanes design (V₅₄–V₅₈) were calculated in linear meters while
254 multimodal transportation lane types (V₅₉–V₆₃), intersection priorities (V₆₄–V₆₆), number of public transit
255 routes (V₇₅) and public parking (V₇₆–V₈₁) were directly counted and expressed as ‘#’ (see Fig. S2).
256 Further urban features concerning the transportation network, such as the maximum speed limit (V₆₇)
257 was expressed in km/h, and the parking ratio (V₈₂) was calculated as a proportion relative to the length
258 of the road in meters.

259 Furthermore, built environment elements such as average number of floors (V_{83}) and estimative height
260 of the building alongside urban roads (V_{84}) were reported for each street in linear meters. Instead,
261 predominant transverse section geometry (V_{85}), pavement material and its condition (V_{86} – V_{87}) were
262 categorically registered for each road expressed as '&'. The transverse sections were defined as type 'U'
263 if there were buildings on both sides, type 'L' if only one side had buildings, and type '-' in the case with
264 no buildings around. The pavement materials were identified as '1' for asphalt, '2' for concrete, '3' for
265 soil or '4' for cobblestones. The surface condition of the pavement was also classified as '1' for good
266 condition, '2' for normal state, and '3' for damaged pavement.

267 Finally, demographic burden urban features were extracted from each block as it is the most precise
268 geographical unit available directly from Census data. A block is formed by at least four occupied
269 dwellings with dwellers present (INE, 2018). Total population (V_{88}), total housing (V_{89}), residential
270 houses (V_{90}), and residential apartments (V_{91}) were assigned as urban features related to the inhabitants
271 of the surrounding area since these are data collected from the people effectively censused.

272 Average road traffic noise was measured in 150 sampling points (see Fig. 1). Two or three noise
273 measurements were performed during the daytime of different workdays, each measured over a period
274 of 15 minutes, to obtain the A-weighted equivalent continuous sound level (L_{Aeq}) in dB. Previous studies
275 have shown that this number of measurements is sufficient to characterize the daytime period and how
276 this daytime period is the most representative of the average annual sound environment (Rey Gozalo et
277 al., 2013b; Prieto & Barrigón, 2015). A Class 1 sound level meter was placed at equidistant locations
278 along the road. The ISO 1996-2 standard (ISO, 2017) was used to define the location of the measuring
279 equipment and for measuring under favorable weather conditions. The sound level meter was calibrated
280 correctly before and after each measurement.

281 2.3. Data processing

282 Due to the different lengths of the sampled urban roads (L_r) and the different extension of the dwelling's
283 blocks exposed to the assessed road (L_{fb}), a standardization of the registered urban feature was
284 implemented as Eq. (1). This equation was used for the following discrete numerical urban variables:
285 temporary residence (V_5), commercial (V_{16}), religious (V_{19}), cultural (V_{24}), sport (V_{28}), educational (V_{34}),
286 health (V_{38}), security (V_{41}), service (V_{44}), community (V_{45}), transportation infrastructure (V_{53}), traffic
287 lights (V_{68}), crosswalks (V_{69}), speed bump (V_{70}), transit stops (V_{73}), taxi stops (V_{74}) and parking ratio (V_{82}).

$$U_r = U_d / L_r, \quad (1)$$

288 where U_d is the discrete urban feature and L_r is the road length (km).

289 The demographic urban features associated with the block extension (V_{88} , V_{89} , V_{90} and V_{91}) were
290 normalized defining data by block facades (U_{rb}) by using the open-source software QGIS and Eq. (2). A
291 similar procedure has been employed in previous studies (Rey Gozalo et al., 2012).

$$U_{rb} = \sum_{b=1}^u \left(\frac{U_b}{A_b} \right) \left(\frac{L_{fb}}{L_r} \right) \quad (2)$$

292 where r and b denote road and block, respectively, U_b is the block urban feature, A_b is the block area (ha),
293 L_{fb} is the block façade length facing the road (m), and L_r is the road length (m).

294 With the normalized urban features, three different models were studied. Model 1 analyzed the urban
295 stratification with the previously defined five types of urban roads (C1, C2, C3, C4, and C5) (Rey Gozalo
296 et al., 2020) (see Fig. 1). Previous studies had shown that some cities where road categories C1 and C2
297 are not frequent in the road network, have significant differentiation problems (Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a).
298 In addition, the analysis of the historical morphology of the city of Valdivia has shown that road
299 categories C1 and C2 have the same level of global integration, so they are the least segregated roads in

300 the city favoring movement and connectivity (Zumelzu et al., 2016). On the basis of these previous
301 studies and considering Valdivia as an intermediate scale city (Zumelzu & Barrientos-Trinanes, 2019), a
302 Model 2 with four types of roads was defined: C1+C2, C3, C4, and C5 (see Fig. 3a).

303 Lastly, from the point of view of sound perception, and considering the results obtained in previous
304 studies (Montes González et al., 2023; Ren et al; 2023), significant differences in noise annoyance were
305 detected by distinguishing between main roads and residential roads. These results are also aligned with
306 urban activity patterns in the city (Zumelzu et al., 2016). Thus, Model 3 was developed considering three
307 types of road classification: C1+C2+C3, C4, and C5 (see Fig. 3b).

308 **Fig. 3.** Geographical representation of the different types of urban roads used in Model 2(a) and Model 3(b).

309 The road classification of the models is categorical and ordinal regarding road traffic noise (see Fig. 5).
310 Also, some of the urban features analyzed do not comply with normal distribution. Therefore,
311 nonparametric statistical inference tests were implemented.

312 A multivariate ordered logistic regression (logit) analysis was performed to estimate the probability of
313 road classification by its urban features. Similar procedure has been applied in previous urban studies for

314 transport demand estimation (LaMondia et al., 2014; Mwale et al., 2022), quantifying the subjective
315 perception of the soundscape (Yang, 2019), and in social science studies related to behavioral preference
316 choices (Menard, 2002; Borooah, 2002).

317 Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ) was calculated to verify the non-existence of multicollinearity,
318 and 28 statistically independent urban features were selected $0 < |\rho| < 0.8$. Finally, for each model, the
319 proportional odds of the independent variables were validated. The test of parallel lines was conducted
320 to verify the statistical assumption on the equal slopes in the coefficients of the logistic regression floating
321 estimators. Proportional odds analysis is necessary to find the minimum number of independent variables
322 (urban features) to allow the estimator to account for all the probabilities of category choice (road
323 categories) equally with one equation per model.

324 3. Results

325 3.1. Sound level stratification

326 This section presents an analysis of the sound levels recorded in each of the road categories proposed in
327 the three models mentioned above (Model 1, 2, and 3). The median values and their dispersion are shown
328 in Fig. 4a.

329

330

331

(b)

332

333

Fig. 4. Box plot (a) and results of ROC analysis (b) for of L_{Aeq} (dB) measured in urban road categories.

334

Table 1

335

p -Values with *BY* adjustment of pairwise comparisons of urban road categories using Mann-Whitney *U* test.

Road category	C1	C2	C1+C2	C3	C1+C2+C3	C4
C2	0.013					
C1+C2	0.226	0.459				
C3	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001			
C1+C2+C3	0.003	0.259	0.004	0.003		
C4	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
C5	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

336

337

338

339

340

341

342

There are no significant differences in the median noise values registered in C1 (73.5 ± 1.7 dBA), C2 (72.7 ± 0.7 dBA), and C1+C2 (73.2 ± 0.8 dBA) for the road categories with the highest noise levels in models 1 and 2, as shown in Fig. 4a and Table 1. The difference of the median values is less than 1 dBA for these three types of road categories, and they have a low dispersion (interquartile range). However, the model 3 major road category C1+C2+C3 has a median of 72.2 dBA and exhibits a larger dispersion (± 2.9 dBA). Therefore, category C1+C2+C3 shows significant differences in their mean values compared to the categories C1, C2 and C1+C2. Regarding Category 3, which corresponds to urban roads giving

343 access to areas of interest or villages, it is shown as a differentiated stratum in the three models.
344 Categories 4 and 5 correspond to residential streets, although Category 4 generally records a higher traffic
345 flow, as it is the main access and exit street for that neighborhood. Noise levels of Category C4 are around
346 65.9 dBA (± 3.8 dBA). The road category C5 was the quietest, with 56.5 dBA of road traffic noise,
347 although it exhibited the most dispersed level ranges (± 7.1 dBA).

348 In addition to the study of the stratification of the median sound levels registered in each road category,
349 the sensitivity, non-specificity, and predictive performance of the sound values registered in each road
350 category were analyzed, and the results are shown in Fig. 4b. According to previous studies, this analysis
351 has provided more precise information on the classification of the registered sound values (Farahani et
352 al., 2022; Zambon et al., 2016; Rey-Gozalo & Barrigón Morillas, 2016).

353 Although the five road categories present significant differences in median L_{Aeq} (dB) values, as shown in
354 Fig. 4a and Table 1, the predictive capacity and sensitivity percentages of Category 1 and Category 2
355 increase significantly when combined, as shown in Fig. 4b. The new road category (C1+C2) does not
356 have significant differences concerning categories C1 and C2 (see Table 2). The decrease in non-
357 specificity due to this combination is insignificant, as these values were already very low for the separate
358 categories. Regarding the combination of the noise levels measured in category C1+C2+C3, the
359 significant predictive capacity increase of C1+C2+C3 concerning C1+C2 is minimal (see Fig. 4b).

360 3.2. *Developed models*

361 Table 2 shows the three different urban features-based models to predict Valdivia's urban roads
362 categorization and their comparison with outcome predictor urban features. Model thresholds, McFadden
363 pseudo- R^2 fitting and proportional odds of each multinomial ordered logistic regression test for a 95%
364 statistical level of significance are also included in the analysis.

365 An efficient selection of urban features was conducted to develop the three models in Table 2. Therefore,
366 the minimum quantity of urban features was included in calculating the floating estimators of the same
367 slopes in the coefficients for each model separately. Non-significant urban features involved in the
368 models are the minimum number necessary to validate the proportional odds assumption using tests of
369 parallel lines.

370 Firstly, urban features of commercial and community equipment building use (V_{16} and V_{45}), several
371 multimodal urban transportations such as infrastructure (V_{53}), geometrical design of lanes (V_{54} , V_{55} , V_{57} ,
372 and V_{62}), security elements (V_{68}), effective transit route (V_{75}), parking ratio (V_{82}), as well as urban
373 features related to the inhabitants of the surrounding area (V_{90}), were the most statistically significant
374 urban features for the developed models. However, urban features related to others equipment building
375 use (V_{34} , V_{41} , and V_{44}), green areas (V_{47}), exclusive multimodal transportation lane types for bicycles
376 (V_{60}) and public buses (V_{61}), crosswalks (V_{69}), taxi stops (V_{74}) and the average building height (V_{84})
377 along the built environment, were relevant inputs for the statistical models.

378 On the other hand, the main difference between developed models was their quantity of variables since
379 the three models exhibited similar fitting. Models 1 and 2 also had comparable proportional odds results
380 except Model 3. Thus, Model 1 predicts urban roads using a road categorization method with 20 urban
381 features. Model 2 needs 14 predictors of urban features, and Model 3 requires only six independent
382 variables. It is worth mentioning that Model 1 allows the prediction of five urban road categories. Thus,
383 it needs more independent variables even though some of its urban features are statistically non-
384 significant.

385
386

Table 2
Multinomial ordered logistic regression results.

Multinomial ordered logistic regression urban features				
ID	Urban feature	<i>Model 1</i>	<i>Model 2</i>	<i>Model 3</i>
V ₁₆	Commercial eq.	(*)	(**)	
V ₃₄	Educational eq.	(n.s.)	(n.s.)	
V ₄₁	Security eq.	(n.s.)		
V ₄₄	Service eq.	(n.s.)	(n.s.)	
V ₄₅	Community eq.	(*)	(*)	
V ₄₇	Green areas	(n.s.)		
V ₅₃	Transportation inf.	(*)	(**)	(n.s.)
V ₅₄	Length of road	(***)	(**)	(***)
V ₅₅	Median width	(n.s.)	(n.s.)	(**)
V ₅₇	Sidewalk width	(*)	(**)	(*)
V ₆₀	Bicycle lane	(n.s.)	(n.s.)	
V ₆₁	Public bus lane	(n.s.)		
V ₆₂	Personal car lane	(*)	(**)	
V ₆₈	Traffic light	(n.s.)		(***)
V ₆₉	Crosswalks	(n.s.)		
V ₇₄	Taxi stops	(n.s.)		
V ₇₅	Transit route	(***)	(***)	(***)
V ₈₂	Parking ratio	(*)	(**)	
V ₈₄	Building height	(n.s.)	(n.s.)	
V ₉₀	Residential houses	(*)	(*)	
Thresholds		$\delta_1 = -17.718$ $\delta_2 = -12.875$ $\delta_3 = -9.989$ $\delta_4 = -6.381$	$\delta_1 = -13.377$ $\delta_2 = -10.463$ $\delta_3 = -7.018$	$\delta_1 = -11.738$ $\delta_2 = -7.529$
Model Fitting McFadden pseudo-R ² (R ² _{McFadden})		0.504	0.492	0.593
Proportional odds: Test of parallel lines (χ^2)		0.997	0.984	0.247

n.s.: non-significant difference $p > 0.05$
 *: p-value ≤ 0.05
 **: p-value ≤ 0.01
 ***: p-value ≤ 0.001

387 Regarding the results shown in Table 2, although Model 3 has the highest $R^2_{McFadden}$, the three models
 388 had relevant goodness-of-fit because 0.6 is the maximum value McFadden pseudo- R^2 (Domencich &
 389 McFadden, 1975). Test of parallel lines null hypothesis states that the slope coefficients in the model are
 390 the same across response roads categories. Therefore, the significance of the models should be close to
 391 1. Thresholds are illustrated in Fig. 5. Latent variables (Z_i) of each model and their categorization are
 392 shown in Eqs. (3), (4), and (5). Subsequently, Eqs. (6), (7), and (8) (Menard, 2002) are used to illustrate
 393 the predicted probabilities of the developed models.

394

395

Fig. 5. Probability distribution of developed categorization models.

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_{i,model\ 1} = & -0.032V_{16,i} - 0.076V_{34,i} + 0.240V_{41,i} + 0.065V_{44,i} - 0.581V_{45,i} + 0.007V_{47,i} \\
& -0.448V_{53,i} - 0.003V_{54,i} + 0.232V_{55,i} - 0.262V_{57,i} - 0.740V_{60,i} + 2.602V_{61,i} \\
& -0.881V_{62,i} - 0.091V_{68,i} - 0.129V_{69,i} - 0.131V_{74,i} - 0.778V_{75,i} + 0.019V_{82,i} \\
& -0.134V_{84,i} + 0.023V_{90,i}
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_{i,model\ 2} = & -0.031V_{16,i} - 0.238V_{34,i} + 0.081V_{44,i} - 0.597V_{45,i} - 0.494V_{53,i} - 0.002V_{54,i} \\
& +0.260V_{55,i} - 0.339V_{57,i} - 1.253V_{60,i} - 0.979V_{62,i} - 0.793V_{75,i} + 0.022V_{82,i} \\
& -0.226V_{84,i} + 0.022V_{90,i}
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

$$Z_{i,model\ 3} = -0.441V_{53,i} - 0.007V_{54,i} + 0.466V_{55,i} - 0.381V_{57,i} - 0.611V_{68,i} - 1.176V_{75,i} \tag{5}$$

396 Latent variable ($Z_{i,model\ 1}$) of Model 1 in Eq. (3) depends on 20 urban features, while Model 2 in Eq. (4)
397 ($Z_{i,model\ 2}$) needs 14 variables, and model 3 requires only 6 urban features to estimate the classification
398 trough Eq. (5) ($Z_{i,model\ 3}$).

$$P(C = m) = 1 / (1 + e^{(Z_i - \delta_m)}), m = 1 \tag{6}$$

$$P(C = m) = 1 / (1 + e^{(Z_i - \delta_m)}) - \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} (1 / (1 + e^{(Z_i - \delta_j)})), m = 2, \dots, (M - 1) \tag{7}$$

$$P(C = m) = 1 - (1 / (1 + e^{(Z_i - \delta_{m-1})})), m = M \tag{8}$$

399 where C is the road category of the model, m is the ordinal road category, Z_i is the floating estimator
400 result of the road (i), δ_m is the threshold of the category by model, and M is the last road category number
401 of each model (ordinal).

402 The graphical representation of Eqs. (6), (7), and (8) of each model shown in Fig. 5 complement the
403 floating estimators presented in Eqs. (3), (4), and (5). Logistic distribution curves have different
404 thresholds (δ_m) at a 95% confidence level, which delimit the probability ranges of classification of each

405 road category for each model (see Eqs. (3), (4), and (5)). Therefore, the predictive ability of the model is
406 better if the thresholds of the different categories are distant from each other. In short, the prediction
407 procedure of the developed models first requires the calculation of the latent variable (Z_i) through the
408 urban features of each road by using Eqs. (6), (7), or (8), and then placing the result in Fig. 5, analyzing
409 from left to right, since by condition the dependent variables are ordinal. In this case, the road categories
410 of all models are ordinal decreasing regarding road traffic noise (see Fig. 4a). For instance, in the Model
411 1 scenario, the probability of the urban road being C1 is assessed first, then if it is C2, and so on until C4
412 is discarded and C5 is assigned. When a road scores $Z=-17$, it has a 30% probability of being C1, but as
413 it fits after the thresholds ($\delta_1 = -17.718$), it is assigned to category C2 with a 70% probability.

414 In general, all the developed models have an excellent capacity to assign higher categories. The first
415 threshold of Model 2 ($\delta_1 = -13.377$) and the second threshold of Model 1 ($\delta_2 = -12.875$) are
416 practically identical. Hence, this result shows that the urban characteristics determining road category
417 C1+C2 of Model 2 are very similar to road category C2 of Model 1. Regarding the choice between C2
418 and C3, Model 2 outperforms the predictive ability of Model 1, starting with probability levels of 55%
419 compared to 40% for Model 1. On the other hand, Models 1 and 2 were less accurate in distinguishing
420 road categories C3 and C4 as the probability is less than 40% of the difference between the discarded
421 and the assigned road category.

422 The predictive ability of road categories C4 and C5 in Models 1 and 3 was the same, both starting with
423 a 50% probability, while Model 2 was more than 20% accurate. It is essential to mention that in model
424 3, when the result of the latent variable (Z_i) for a road was between -11.6 and -10.3, it is categorized as
425 C4 even if the probabilities of it being a main road C1+C2+C3 are between 20% and 40%.

426 According to the results presented below, Model 2 is more efficient than Model 1 for a city such as
427 Valdivia because, with only 14 urban characteristics, it can classify roads ordered decreasingly

428 concerning their traffic noise. In addition, Model 2 has the same classification performance as Model 1
429 for roads C3 and C4. Furthermore, Model 2 allows the identification of road category C5 with a higher
430 probability percentage than Models 1 and 3.

431 *3.3. Urban features significance*

432 This section presents the results of calculating the marginal probabilities from the mean of the
433 determinant variables of the developed models. These results determine the likelihood of road category
434 change by varying the value of a single unit of a given urban feature.

435 For Model 1, which consists of five road categories (C1, C2, C3, C4, and C5), Fig. 6a and Table S2
436 shows the results of calculating the marginal effects of its 20 urban features. Overall, Model 1 does not
437 perform well in estimating C1 roads, as the unit change of any urban feature practically does not affect
438 its categorization choice. Instead, for the C2 road category classification, the transit lane (V_{61}) and the
439 personal vehicle lane (V_{62}) were involved. Subsequently, the unitary change of urban features of
440 multimodal urban transportation elements related to road design (V_{60} , V_{61} , V_{62}) and public transport
441 routes (V_{75}) are the most relevant for C3 road type estimation. In addition to the multimodal urban
442 transportation element already mentioned, C4 and C5 road types are defined by urban features elements
443 focused on driving and walking experience (V_{55} , V_{57} , V_{68} , V_{69} , and V_{74}), public parking ratio (V_{82}),
444 transportation infrastructure (V_{53}), urban equipment (V_{16} , V_{34} , V_{41} , V_{44} , and V_{45}), built environment
445 elements (V_{84}), and residential houses (V_{90}).

446 Fig. 6b and Table S3 shows the results of calculating the marginal effects of the 14 urban features of
447 Model 2, which consists of four types of urban roads (C1+C2, C3, C4, and C5). The unitary change of
448 urban elements such as infrastructure features for transport modes (V_{53}), for walking use (V_{55} and V_{57}),
449 for cyclists (V_{60}), personal motorized vehicles (V_{62}), and public buses (V_{75}) affects the classification of
450 the new road category C1+C2 and in category C3 of Model 2. In addition, the presence of social and

451 community facilities impacts categories C3 and C4. On the other hand, C5 roads are influenced mainly
 452 by sustainable transport infrastructure (buses and cycling) and less by educational, social, and community
 453 facilities due to the insufficient mix of adequate land uses in residential areas.

454 (a)

455 (b)
 456

457

458

(c)

459

460

Fig. 6. Urban features marginal effects of Model 1 (a), Model 2 (b), and Model 3 (c).

461

462

463

464

465

466

467

468

469

Clustering C1 and C2 has increased the distinction of this new road classification from other roads while enhancing the differentiation between categories C3 and C4, which in Valdivia are more diverse regarding people's daily activities in the city. A variety of commercial and educational activities, use of services, and social and community events are facilitated by transit and transport infrastructure, including parking facilities, which can be considered the "real trip destination" for people traveling in their private motorized vehicles (ITE, 2010). Thereby, C4 roads are defined as mixed-in effective land uses by combining housing, retail, services, and pedestrian infrastructure. These urban features in neighborhoods promote social interaction as they involve more people on the roads compared to residential-only areas (Zumelzu & Barrientos-Trinanes, 2019).

470

471

472

473

474

475

Finally, Fig. 6c and Table S4 shows the marginal effects of the six urban features of Model 3 based on three types of urban roads ((C1+C2+C3), C4, and C5). The urban feature transit routes (V₇₅) is the most relevant for categorizing all the road types in Model 3. The unit increase in transit routes along with traffic lights, transportation infrastructure, and median and sidewalk width are the most critical contributors to defining roads in the C1+C2+C3 category and, consequently, the highest road traffic noise levels. Instead, if a road has mostly transit routes and traffic lights, the road category will be C4.

476

477

Mobility in future cities is based on the daily use of public transportation systems and active modes of transport such as cycling and walking (Li et al, 2023), especially in intermediated cities where population

478 growth requires investment in infrastructure to improve accessibility and reduce emissions (UN-Habitat,
479 2022). The necessary interventions to achieve a sustainable transport system are aligned with the
480 distribution of public transport routes along walkable paths from dwellings. These improvements will
481 also contribute to reducing noise exposure on the population along residential roads, since in Model 3,
482 the presence of public transit routes characterized C4 roads, which connect the C5 roads with the rest of
483 the main roads in the city. At the same time, proper sidewalk and median widths promote pedestrian use
484 of the streets (Li et al, 2023; ITE, 2010). They can be modified to reduce the levels of road traffic noise
485 exposure experienced by their users (Echevarria Sanchez et al., 2016; Ren et al., 2023).

486 Model 3 indicates which roads are likely to be saturated with traffic noise through the simple
487 identification of routes designed entirely for motorized transport infrastructure (C1+C2+C3) by
488 collecting only six urban features. Furthermore, the model segregates road C4, whose urban features
489 promote the diversity and mix of uses associated with city life. In addition, it identifies those C5 roads
490 related to areas that require protection from road traffic noise due to the resting and recreational activities
491 in these zones.

492 **4. Discussion**

493 *4.1. Road traffic noise of the street categories*

494 Given the fact that the design of cities is mostly oriented towards car use (ITE, 2010), noise values
495 exceeding 70 dB are common in South American and European cities (Suárez & Barros, 2014; Quiñones-
496 Bolaños et al., 2016; Bastián-Monarca et al., 2016; Mary Paiva et al., 2019; Bravo-Moncayo et al., 2019;
497 Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a). The findings of the study show that there were no significant differences in
498 the median noise values registered in the road categories with the highest noise levels in Models 1 and 2
499 (C1, C2, and C1+C2). In cities where categories C1 and C2 are not extensive, noise prediction is less
500 accurate (Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a). Also, the urban morphology of roads C1 and C2 represent the most

501 integrated roads segments in Valdivia ([Zumelzu et al., 2016](#)); their functionality is to be the primary and
502 alternative access to the city, as well to provide access to its main distribution nodes and point of interest.

503 Instead, C1+C2+C3 show significant differences in their mean values compared to the mentioned road
504 classes. Hence, from a noise point of view, this clustering has no advantages over the C1+C2 category.
505 However, from the point of view of sustainable urban and transport planning, the separation of main
506 roads (C1+C2+C3) from residential roads (C4 and C5) could guide local governments to determine
507 priority zones of the city to invest and manage to protect sensitive receivers from traffic noise exposure,
508 reducing its health risks and annoyance on the inhabitants and pedestrians ([Montes González et al., 2023](#);
509 [Ren et al., 2023](#)).

510 Urban roads categorized as C4 and C5 correspond to residential streets. Although, the functionality of
511 C4 is the main residential access and exit for neighborhoods, these streets had higher traffic flow than
512 C5 and noise fluctuating between the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)
513 limit defined for environmental noise exposure and the typical noise level of a normal conversation
514 ([Crocker & Arenas, 2021](#)). Classifying urban streets with noise levels below 65 dBA allows to identify
515 places where the perception of the acoustics environment could be improved by intervening on the
516 amount of visible greenery in urban landscapes ([Ren et al., 2023](#)).

517 In general, C5 roads were the quietest and with the most dispersed traffic noise levels. The sound
518 variability in this type of road is expected due to the low traffic flow ([Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a](#); [Bastián-
519 Monarca et al., 2016](#)). Therefore, in urban context to obtain less variability on noise levels in residential
520 streets it is recommended to carry out road traffic noise measurements of at least 1 hour ([Brambilla et
521 al., 2023](#)). Nevertheless, in Valdivia city they had high levels of dispersion due to the presence of heavy
522 public transit lines (urban buses) on some of these roads. These findings result from a lack of
523 transportation planning and assessment of its potential environmental and health impacts on the

524 population. Road traffic noise must be integrated into the urban and transportation planning of cities,
525 especially in the design of transit routes for the protection of sensitive receivers such as residences, health
526 care, and educational facilities.

527 4.2. Potential application of the developed models

528 Broadly speaking, the urban characteristics that represent the main roads (C1, C2, C3, and their
529 combination) are the presence of dedicated lanes for public transportation, personal motor vehicles,
530 bicycle lanes, public transit routes, traffic lights, wide sidewalks, transportation infrastructure and public
531 facilities such as community, public safety, educational, and utilities. These urban features involve traffic
532 noise levels above 70 dBA measured near the road. Furthermore, when a road is predominantly used by
533 public transit routes, including exclusive transportation and bicycle lanes, it is more likely to be a
534 category C4 with median daytime traffic noise exposure levels of 65 dBA. By acquiring the mentioned
535 urban features and by choosing the most appropriate model for the city context, it is possible to cluster
536 similar streets to allow urban and transportation planners to support the reduction of people's noise
537 exposure.

538 Different studies worldwide have found significant relationships between urban form and road noise
539 pollution (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2018). Noise mapping (Montalvão et al., 2011; Wang & Kang, 2011;
540 Weber et al., 2014; Margaritis & Kang, 2016; Yu & Kang, 2017; Kim et al., 2019) and *in situ* noise
541 measurements (Han et al., 2018; Hong & Jeon, 2017; Lu et al., 2019) have been used to analyze some
542 separately urban features and morphology effects in road traffic noise. Furthermore, statistical modeling
543 techniques, deep learning, and geographical information on urban features have been combined with
544 traffic volume to estimate urban road traffic noise maps (Hunjae et al., 2017; Lu et al., 2019; Song et al.,
545 2024). Previous results show that some of the urban features selected in the models of this research have
546 been part of predictor variables in urban noise studies. However, such a complete and diverse data

547 collection of urban features had not been used before. Additionally, these urban features are not directly
548 related to source sound power, source type, or propagation path. Regardless, they are important for
549 understanding urban environments and contribute to established physical models and noise calculation
550 methods.

551 Although some urban features were not statistically significant in the developed models, some authors
552 have reported evidence of how these variables influence traffic noise and urban functions. Green areas
553 were one of the variables to explain traffic noise distribution calculated from noise maps (Margaritis &
554 Kang, 2016). Furthermore, building height was one of the most critical urban form indicators for
555 predicting road traffic noise levels with artificial neural networks and ordinary least-squares (Kim et al.,
556 2019). This value has been used to calculate landscape metrics, which are more useful and fit statistically
557 better than structural parameters to predict the highest noise levels and air pollution (Weber et al., 2014).
558 Moreover, the number of building floors was an underlined urban feature to design streets to minimize
559 the effects of traffic noise in urban areas (Montalvão et al., 2011).

560 Additionally, the presence or absence of traffic lights affects traffic noise intensity due to drivers
561 accelerating or decelerating in the middle of the street between important intersections (Lu et al., 2019).
562 Urban features supporting multimodal transportation infrastructure, such as bicycle lanes and taxi and
563 bus stops, point out the availability of travel modes, which are critical factors influencing travel demand
564 in developing cities (Mwale et al., 2022). They are directly associated with bus lanes, significantly
565 affecting noise level prediction (Adulaimi et al., 2021), and their design could help reduce pedestrians'
566 and urban cyclists' noise exposure (Echevarria Sanchez et al., 2016). On the other hand, the location of
567 crosswalks on streets and median widths have been considered in sustainable urban planning design
568 because they modulate and promote walkability (Li et al., 2023). Typically, educational, security, and
569 service institutions are points of interest in cities, determining the daily mobility of many people
570 traveling; therefore, they are usually destinations and considered trip generators (ITE, 2010).

571 While green areas, building height, traffic lights, bicycle lanes, taxi stops, bus lanes, crosswalks, median
572 widths, and educational, security, and service equipment may not significantly impact individually, their
573 collective influence is crucial in validating the developed models and understanding how multiple factors
574 shape urban functions. These findings underscore the complexity of urban and transportation systems,
575 emphasizing the necessity of considering multiple urban features in exploring the relationship between
576 road traffic noise and urban planning.

577 Model 1 is recommended for developed cities with extensive transportation networks and urban
578 characteristics of C1. In intermediate cities where urban expansion is expected to occur, Model 2 is the
579 most appropriate. This is due to the opportunities for transportation and urban intervention in the road
580 network and their built environment by using new technologies to prevent high noise exposure over the
581 future population. In summary, the choice between Model 1 or Model 2 depends on the scale of the city.
582 On a complementary basis, Model 3 could be applied at any city scale but with a focus on local
583 administration.

584 It is well known that the primary noise source in cities is road traffic, but it has been found that urban
585 features of streets also have an important influence on the distribution of noise in a city. Consequently,
586 the developed models have the potential to be employed as a management tool for urban and
587 transportation planners to stratified road categories influenced mainly by transportation infrastructure
588 present in all occidental cities ([ITE, 2010](#)) and facilities dependent on urban planning at local levels ([UN-
589 Habitat, 2022](#)). Some applications might include: to identify roads in the network that require
590 interventions in their infrastructure and transit routes to prevent high levels of traffic noise exposure to
591 the population residing in urban areas in the future, to simulate actions in the road network and the built
592 environment by utilizing new technologies, as stated by Shaygan et al. ([Shaygan et al., 2022](#)) and Song
593 et al. ([Song et al., 2024](#)), among others.

594 The developed models do not aim to replace the calculation methods for noise mapping. These models
595 can be used in urban sound planning to identify locations where noise measurement sensors could be
596 installed to inform citizens about road traffic noise indicators, to optimize road traffic noise measurement
597 campaigns to validate the predictions from noise models ([Brambilla et al., 2023](#)), to assess urban areas
598 where road traffic data is not available, to provide a detailed description of the elements supporting the
599 multimodal transportation system, a contextualization of the built environment and points of interest
600 among others to create and distribute trips in road traffic models (Codeca et al., 2020), to manage urban
601 facilities' location to redistribute road traffic noise as an alternative or complement to the standard
602 mitigation methods such as noise barriers, noise control on building facades and low-noise pavements
603 ([Ranpise & Tandel, 2022](#)), and to design urban soundwalk with the aim to avoid or address the
604 soundscape of an acoustic environment with a high predominance of traffic noise but also to identify
605 quiet areas to be protected and valorized. It is necessary to intensify current mitigation measures to reduce
606 the number of people exposed to noise levels harmful to health. Proper urban planning will be a powerful
607 tool to reduce noise, and these models provide urban managers with information on the urbanistic
608 variables that most influence road functionality and, consequently, their noise levels.

609 The development of this kind of models represents an important contribution to the sustainable planning.
610 Intermediate cities will experience the most significant growth in population and urbanization over the
611 next 30 years. At the same time, they are the cities with the most important lack of transport infrastructure,
612 poor economic diversity, and low capacity to implement public environmental policies ([UN-Habitat,](#)
613 [2022](#)). These conditions make them less competitive for investment, involving insufficient job
614 opportunities and raising the need to travel by private car from residential houses to workplaces out of
615 the city. Therefore, integrate the road traffic noise as part of the urban planning leads to manage and
616 prevent the imminent increasing of traffic flow, congestion, noise pollution and its adverse effect on
617 health and quality of life.

618 **5. Conclusions**

619 Ninety-one urban features and road traffic noise were measured in 140 streets in the city of Valdivia,
620 Chile. Three models were described to analyze the urban functionality of the city roads: Model 1
621 considered the five classes categorization developed in previous studies (C1, C2, C3, C4 and C5);
622 additionally, results from other urban studies conducted in the city were examined to describe a Model 2
623 with four classes (C1+C2, C3, C4 and C5); subsequently, a Model 3 with three categories (C1+C2+C3,
624 C4 and C5) was also analyzed considering results in other cities on the perception of noise annoyance.

625 A tool applicable to developed and growing cities based on typical urban data on city streets has been
626 created. This methodology allows to classify city urban roads by their functionality by only their urban
627 features through three different probabilistic models which support the classification of city roads. Model
628 1, 2, and 3 differ in their number of explanatory variables, with 20, 14, and 6 urban features, respectively.
629 Furthermore, all the models show a strong goodness of fit in terms of McFadden pseudo- R^2 ranging
630 between 0.5 and 0.6, equivalent to a coefficient of determination R^2 greater than 0.8. In general, the
631 elements of the urban form associated with higher road traffic noise are those related to the availability
632 of multimodal transportation lanes with places for community activities. Currently, all these urban
633 features are recommended factors to address in urban and transportation planning for sustainable cities.
634 Despite this, previous studies have analyzed the effect of urban features on road traffic noise
635 independently. Therefore, this study represents an advancement in the integrated assessment of multiple
636 city-level features. The findings provide a valuable contribution and have the potential to be used as a
637 management tool for urban and transportation planners to the understanding of the urban sound
638 environment.

639 **Acknowledgements**

640 This research was funded by Chilean National Agency for Research and Development (ANID) through
641 the project FONDECYT No. 1180547, and by the Faculty of Engineering Sciences (FCI) at the
642 University Austral of Chile (UACH) through the InnovING 2030 mobility scholarship and applied
643 research grant. The authors greatly appreciate the additional support provided by project
644 ANID/FONDEQUIP (Grant EQM150108). The authors thank Antonio Zumelzu and Andrea Báez for
645 sharing their knowledge for this study. Appreciation also goes to Jeffrey LaMondia and Fernando
646 Cordero for introducing urban features analysis techniques employed in travel behavior and
647 transportation forecasting and supporting systematizing geographic information. Special mention to
648 Daniela Burgos for his help in the visual abstract design.

649 **References**

- 650 Adulaimi, A. A., Pradhan, B., Chakraborty, S., & Alamri, A. (2021). Traffic Noise Modelling Using
651 Land Use Regression Model Based on Machine Learning, Statistical Regression and GIS.
652 *Energies*, *14*(5095). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14165095>.
- 653 Barrigón Morillas, J. M., Rey Gozalo, G., Montes González, D., Atanasio Moraga, P., & Vílchez-Gómez,
654 R. (2018). Noise Pollution and Urban Planning. *Current Pollution Reports*, *4*, 208-219.
655 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40726-018-0095-7>.
- 656 Bastián-Monarca, N. A., Suárez, E., & Arenas, J. P. (2016). Assessment of methods for simplified traffic
657 noise mapping of small cities: Casework of the city of Valdivia, Chile. *Science of the Total*
658 *Environment*, *550*, 439–448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.01.139>.
- 659 Blanes, N., Fons-Esteve, J., Hintzsche, M., Ramos, M. J., Rööslin, M., Sáinz de la Maza, M., . . . Peris,
660 E. (2022). *Projected health impacts from transportation noise - Exploring two scenarios for 2030*
661 *(Eionet Report - ETC/HE 2022/5)*.
- 662 Borooah, V. K. (2002). *Logit and probit*. Thousand Oaks, California, USA: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- 663 Brambilla, G., Benocci, R., Potenza, A., & Zambon, G. (2023). Stabilization Time of Running Equivalent
664 Level LAeq for Urban Road Traffic Noise. *Applied Sciences*, *13*(207).
665 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13010207>.
- 666 Bravo-Moncayo, L., Chávez, M., Puyana, V., Lucio-Naranjo, J., Garzón, C., & Pavón-García, I. (2019).
667 A cost-effective approach to the evaluation of traffic noise exposure in the city of Quito, Ecuador.
668 *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, *7*, 128–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2018.12.006>.

- 669 Codeca, L., Erdmann, J., Cahill, V., & Haerri, J. SAGA: An Activity-based Multi-modal Mobility
670 Scenario Generator for SUMO. In Proceedings of the SUMO User Conference 2020. From Traffic
671 Flow to Mobility Modeling, Online, October, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.52825/scp.v1i>
- 672 Crocker, M. J., & Arenas, J. P. (2021). *Engineering Acoustics: Noise and Vibration Control* (Vol. I).
673 Chichester, UK: John Wiley and Sons.
- 674 Domencich, T., & McFadden, D. (1975). Statistical Estimation of Choice Probability Functions. In T.
675 Domencich, & D. McFadden, *Urban Travel Demand: A Behavioral Analysis* (pp. 101–125).
676 North-Holland Publishing Co.
- 677 EC (2002). *Directive 2002/49/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 June 2002*
678 *relating to the assessment and management of environmental noise*. European Commission (EC).
679 Official Journal of the European Communities, L 189, volume 45, 18 July 2002.
- 680 EC (2017). *Noise abatement approaches*. Retrieved November 2023, from European Commission (EC).
681 Directorate-General for Environment: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/016648>.
- 682 EC (2022). *Zero pollution: outlook 2022*. Retrieved December 2023, from European Commission (EC).
683 Joint Research Centre (JRC): <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/39491>.
- 684 Echevarria Sanchez, G. M., Van Renterghem, T., Thomas, P., & Botteldooren, D. (2016). The effect of
685 street canyon design on traffic noise exposure along roads. *Building and Environment*, 97, 96–
686 110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.11.033>.
- 687 Farahani, M., Razavi-Termeh, S. V., & Sadeghi-Niarak, A. (2022). A spatially based machine learning
688 algorithm for potential mapping of the hearing senses in an urban environment. *Sustainable Cities*
689 *and Society*, 80(103675). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.103675>.
- 690 Han, X., Huang, X., Liang, H., Ma, S., & Gong, J. (2018). X. Han, X. Huang, H. Liang, S. Ma, J. Gong,
691 Analysis of the relationships between environmental noise and urban morphology.
692 *Environmental Pollution*, 233, 755–765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.10.126>.
- 693 Harouvi, O., Ben-Elia, E., Factor, R., de Hoogh, K., & Kloog, I. (2018). Noise estimation model
694 development using high-resolution transportation and land use regression. *Journal of Exposure*
695 *Science & Environmental Epidemiology*, 28, 559–567. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-018-0035-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-018-0035-z)
696 [z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-018-0035-z).
- 697 Hong, J. Y., & Jeon, J. Y. (2017). Relationships between environmental spatiotemporal variability of
698 soundscape and urban morphology in a multifunctional urban area: A case study in Seoul, Korea.
699 *Building and Environment*, 126, 382–395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2017.10.021>.
- 700 Hunjae, R., In Kwon, P., Bum Seok, C., & Ch. Seo Il, C. (2017). Spatial statistical analysis of the effects
701 of urban form indicators on road-traffic noise exposure of a city in South Korea. *Applied*
702 *Acoustics*, 115, 93–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2016.08.025>.
- 703 INE (2017). *Geodatos abiertos, Microdatos Censo 2017*. Retrieved March 2020, from Instituto Nacional
704 de Estadísticas Chile (INE): [https://ine-](https://ine-chile.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=59ba00b6bab8456cbadf80442b8bea9b)
705 [chile.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=59ba00b6bab8456cbadf80442b8bea9](https://ine-chile.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=59ba00b6bab8456cbadf80442b8bea9b)
706 [b](https://ine-chile.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=59ba00b6bab8456cbadf80442b8bea9b).

- 707 INE (2018). *Manual de usuario de la base de datos del censo de población y vivienda 2017. Chile.*
708 Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas (INE) Chile, Departamento de Demografía y Censos.
- 709 ISO (2017). *ISO 1996-2. Description, Measurement and Assessment of Environmental Noise, Part 2:*
710 *Determination of Environmental Noise Levels.* International Organization for Standardization
711 (ISO), Geneva, Switzerland.
- 712 ITE (2010). *Designing Walkable Urban Thoroughfares: A Context Sensitive Approach. ITE*
713 *Recommended Practice. Publication No. RP-036A.* Institute of Transportation Engineers (ITE).
- 714 Khomenko, S., Cirach, M., Barrera-Gómez, J., Pereira-Barboza, E., Lungman, T., Mueller, N., . . .
715 Nieuwenhuijsen, M. (2022). Impact of road traffic noise on annoyance and preventable mortality
716 in European cities: A health impact assessment. *Environment International*, 162(107160).
717 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107160>.
- 718 Kim, P., Ryu, H., Jeon, J. J., & Chang, S. (2019). Artificial Neural Network Model Development based
719 on Road-traffic Noise and Urban Form Indicators (original full article in Korean). *Transactions*
720 *of the Korean Society for Noise and Vibration Engineering*, 29, 577-583.
721 <https://doi.org/10.5050/KSNVE.2019.29.5.577>.
- 722 Kyprianou, I., Artopoulos, G., Bonomolo, A., Brownlee, T., Ávila Cachado, R., Camaioni, C., . . .
723 Marchesani, G. E. (2023). Mitigation and adaptation strategies to offset the impacts of climate
724 change on urban health: A European perspective. *Building and Environment*, 238(110226).
725 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110226>.
- 726 LaMondia, J. J., Aultman-Hall, L., & Greene, E. (2014). Long-Distance Work and Leisure Travel
727 Frequencies: Ordered Probit Analysis Across Non-Distance-Based Definitions. *Transportation*
728 *Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, 2413(1), 1–12.
729 <https://doi.org/10.3141/2413-01>.
- 730 Li, Y., Yabuki, N., & Fukuda, T. (2023). Integrating GIS, deep learning, and environmental sensors for
731 multicriteria evaluation of urban street walkability. *Landscape and Urban Planning*,
732 230(104603). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2022.104603>.
- 733 Lu, X., Kang, J., Zhu, P., Cai, J., Guo, F., & Zhang, Y. (2019). Influence of urban road characteristics on
734 traffic noise. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 75, 136–155.
735 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2019.08.026>.
- 736 Margaritis, E., & Kang, J. (2016). Relationships between urban green spaces and other features of urban
737 morphology with traffic noise distribution. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 15, 174-185.
738 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2015.12.009>.
- 739 Mary Paiva, K., Alves Cardoso, M. R., & Trombetta Zannin, P. H. (2019). Exposure to road traffic noise:
740 Annoyance, perception and associated factors among Brazil's adult population. *Science of the*
741 *Total Environment*, 650, 978–986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.09.041>.
- 742 Menard, S. (2002). *Applied Logistic Regression Analysis* (Vol. II). Thousand Oaks, California, USA:
743 SAGE Publications, Inc.

- 744 Montalvão, I. C., Bertoli, S. R., & Zannin, P. H. (2011). Influence of urban shapes on environmental
745 noise: A case study in Aracaju–Brazil. *Science of the Total Environment*, 412-413, 66-76.
746 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.10.018>.
- 747 Montes González, D., Barrigón Morillas, J. M., & Rey-Gozaló, G. (2023). Effects of noise on pedestrians
748 in urban environments where road traffic is the main source of sound. *Science of the Total*
749 *Environment*, 857(e159406). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159406>.
- 750 Mwale, M., Luke, R., & Pisa, N. (2022). Factors that affect travel behaviour in developing cities: A
751 methodological review. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 16(100683).
752 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100683>.
- 753 OECD, European Commission, FAO, UN-Habitat, International Labour Organization, and The World
754 Bank (2021). *Applying the Degree of Urbanisation: A Methodological Manual to Define Cities,*
755 *Towns and Rural Areas for International Comparisons*. OECD Regional Development Studies,
756 OECD Publishing, Paris/European Union, Brussels: <https://doi.org/10.1787/4bc1c502-en>.
- 757 Ortúzar, J. D., & Willumsen, L. G. (2011). *Modelling Transport* (Vol. IV). Wiley.
- 758 Prieto Gajardo, C., & Barrigón Morillas, J.M. (2015). Stabilisation patterns of hourly urban sound levels.
759 *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 187, 4072. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-014-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-014-4072-3)
760 [4072-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-014-4072-3).
- 761 Quiñones-Bolaños, E. E., Bustillo-Lecompte, C. F., & Mehrvar, M. (2016). A traffic noise model for
762 road intersections in the city of Cartagena de Indias, Colombia. *Transportation Research Part D:*
763 *Transport and Environment*, 47, 149–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2016.05.007>.
- 764 Ranpise, R. B., & Tandel, B. N. (2022). Urban road traffic noise monitoring, mapping, modelling, and
765 mitigation: A thematic review. *Noise Mapping*, 9, 48-66. [https://doi.org/10.1515/noise-2022-](https://doi.org/10.1515/noise-2022-0004)
766 [0004](https://doi.org/10.1515/noise-2022-0004).
- 767 Ren, X., Li, Q., Yuan, M., & Shao, S. (2023). How visible street greenery moderates traffic noise to
768 improve acoustic comfort in pedestrian environments. *Landscape and Urban Planning*,
769 238(104839). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2023.104839>.
- 770 Rey Gozaló, G., Barrigón Morillas, J. M., & Gómez Escobar, V. (2013a). Urban streets functionality as
771 a tool for urban pollution management. *Science of the Total Environment*, 461–462, 453–461.
772 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.05.017>.
- 773 Rey Gozaló, G., Barrigón Morillas, J. M., Gómez Escobar, V., Vílchez-Gómez, R., Méndez Sierra, J. A.,
774 Carmona del Río, F. J., & Prieto Gajardo, C. (2013b). Study of the categorisation method using
775 long-term measurements. *Archives of Acoustics*, 38, 397–405. [http://dx.doi.org/10.2478/aoa-2013-](http://dx.doi.org/10.2478/aoa-2013-0047)
776 [0047](http://dx.doi.org/10.2478/aoa-2013-0047).
- 777 Rey Gozaló, G., Barrigón Morillas, J. M., & Gómez Escobar, V. (2012). Analysis of noise exposure in
778 two small towns. *Acta Acustica united with Acustica*, 98(6), 884–893.
779 <https://doi.org/10.3813/AAA.918572>.

- 780 Rey Gozalo, G., Suárez, E., Montenegro, A. L., Arenas, J. P., Barrigón Morillas, J. M., & Montes
781 González, D. (2020). Noise Estimation Using Road and Urban Features. *Sustainability*,
782 12(e9217). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219217>.
- 783 Rey-Gozalo, G., & Barrigón Morillas, J. (2016). Analysis of Sampling Methodologies for Noise
784 Pollution Assessment and the Impact on the Population. *International Journal of Environmental*
785 *Research and Public Health*, 13(490). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13050490>.
- 786 Rey-Gozalo, G., Barrigón Morillas, J. M., & Montes González, D. (2022). Analysis and management of
787 current road traffic noise. *Current Pollution Reports*, 8, 315-327. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s40726-
788 022-00234-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40726-022-00234-7).
- 789 Shaygan, M., Meese, C., Li, W., Zhao, X., & Nejad, M. (2022). Traffic prediction using artificial
790 intelligence: Review of recent advances and emerging opportunities. *Transportation Research*
791 *Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 145(103921). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2022.103921>.
- 792 Song, J., Meng, Q., Kang, J., Yang, D., & Li, M. (2024). Effects of planning variables on urban traffic
793 noise at different scales. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 100(105006).
794 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2023.105006>.
- 795 Suárez, E., & Barros, J. L. (2014). Traffic noise mapping of the city of Santiago de Chile. *Science of the*
796 *Total Environment*, 466–467, 539–546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.07.013>.
- 797 UN-Habitat (2022). *World Cities Report 2022: Envisaging the Future of Cities*. Retrieved 2023
798 December, from United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat):
799 https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2022/06/wcr_2022.pdf.
- 800 UN-Habitat (2006). *State of the World's Cities 2006/2007*. Retrieved 2024 April, from United Nations
801 Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat): [https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/download-
802 manager-files/State%20of%20the%20World%E2%80%99s%20Cities%2020062007.pdf](https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/download-manager-files/State%20of%20the%20World%E2%80%99s%20Cities%2020062007.pdf).
- 803 UN (2015). *Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN: A/RES/70/1)*.
804 Retrieved November 2023, from United Nations (UN):
805 <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment>.
- 806 Wang, B., & Kang, J. (2011). Effects of urban morphology on the traffic noise distribution through noise
807 mapping: A comparative study between UK and China. *Applied Acoustics*, 72, 556-568.
808 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2011.01.011>.
- 809 Weber, N., Haase, D., & Franck, U. (2014). Assessing modelled outdoor traffic-induced noise and air
810 pollution around urban structures using the concept of landscape metrics. *Landscape and Urban*
811 *Planning*, 125, 105-116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2014.02.018>.
- 812 WHO (2018). *Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region*. Retrieved October 2023, from
813 World Health Organization (WHO):
814 <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/279952/9789289053563-eng.pdf>.
- 815 Yang, M. (2019). A review of Regression Analysis Methods: establishing the quantitative relationship
816 between subjective Soundscape assessment and multiple factors. *Proceedings of the International*
817 *Congress on Acoustics, ICA2019*, (pp. 6122-6128). Aachen, Germany.

- 818 Yu, W., & Kang, J. (2017). Relationship between traffic noise resistance and village form in China.
819 *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 163, 44-55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2017.02.016>.
- 820 Zambon, G., Benocci, R., & Brambilla, G. (2016). Statistical Road Classification Applied to Stratified
821 Spatial Sampling of Road Traffic Noise in Urban Areas. *International Journal of Environmental*
822 *Research*, 10, 411–420. <https://doi.org/10.22059/ijer.2016.58760>.
- 823 Zumelzu, A., & Barrientos-Trinanes, M. (2019). Analysis of the effects of urban form on neighborhood
824 vitality: five cases in Valdivia, Southern Chile. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*,
825 34, 897–925. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-019-09694-8>.
- 826 Zumelzu, A., Burgos, R., & Navarro, S. (2016). Peripheral expansion and centrality processes in Valdivia
827 between 1900-2015: analysis from the perspective of the Space Syntaxes (original full article in
828 Spanish). *AUS*, 19, 24-30. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4206/aus.2016.n19-05>.

Click here to access/download

Supplementary Material

supplementary material_STOTEN_R1.docx

